

A Study of Attitude of the College Students towards Modernization in Relation to Courses of Study

Poonam Sharma¹ & Km. Sunita Devi²

1. Professor & Head, Department of Teacher Education, J.V Jain College, Saharanpur
Mail id-gkps1234@gmail.com
2. M. Ed Student (2020-2022), J. V. Jain College, Saharanpur (U.P.) India

Received : 01/06/2022

1st BPR : 12/06/2022

2nd BPR : 18/06/2022

Accepted : 22/06/2022

Abstract

Modernization is a socio-cultural process. This is a systematic transformation mechanism involving principles, norms system and framework. The mentally concept, view and behaviour of man are therefore printed to move in the direction. The term modernization is employed not only to identify shift in a nation's materialistic culture, but also in belief system and way of life. Modernization is a process which involves changes in all areas of human thought and activity. It aims at socio-economic and political transformation to achieve progress on development. The research paper is an attempt to study the attitude of college students towards modernization in relation to their courses of study (professional and non-professional). The sample consisted of 60 students studying in various colleges located in Saharanpur, U.P. It was observed that gender and choice of course (professional and non-professional) have no impact on the attitude of college students towards modernization.

Key words: Attitude, Modernization, Course of study.

Introduction

The word modern or modernisation is the derivative of the Latin term 'MODO', which means 'just now' 'or' 'the latest'. The Oxford English Dictionary defines the term 'modern' as 'something of the recent times or something new or latest, not concerned with classic. Thus, the literal meaning of the term refers to anything which is New or Latest in life style, dress, art or thinking.

Modernization is a continuous and open-ended process. Historically, the span of time over which it has occurred must be measured in centuries, although there are examples of accelerated modernization. In either case, modernization is not a once-and-for-all-time achievement. There seems to be a dynamic principle built into the very fabric of modern societies that does not allow them to settle, or to achieve equilibrium. Modernization includes a different behavioural system with certain unique characteristics. It refers to their depth change in way of thinking and feeling. The change witnessed by our society in the last century and the trend of modernization has affected our lives personally. Modernization is the social process. The term modernization doesn't denote any philosophy or movement but only asymbolized process of change. The term modernisation has been severally defined by several eminent scholars and one of them is the Indian sociologist Prof. Y. Singh who writes, "Modernisation symbolizes a rational attitude towards issues and their evaluation from universalistic, not particularistic point of view. To him, Modernisation involves diffusing scientific and technological know-how.

C.E. Black in his book 'Dynamics of Modernisation suggests modernisation as a process by which historically evolved institution are adopted to the rapidly changing function that reflect the unprecedented increase in man's knowledge, permitting control over his environment in the recent centuries that accompanies the scientific revolution.

Education and Modernization are closely related to each other. It is education that can serve as an efficient instrument for effective modernization for a nation to modernize itself, the spread of education in rapid strides is quite essential. It produces the skilled personnel to occupy different positions in life who would contribute for the growth of national wealth through their creative abilities and productive efforts. The importance of the study lies in the fact that modernization plays a role in the enlargement of social awareness. Modernization leads to a desired type of change- social and cultural.

Review of related literature-

Kumar, Sushil (2018) conducted a study of attitude towards modernity and academic achievement of students and found that the dimensions viz marriage, position of women and education have significant and positive correlation with academic achievement. But socio-religious dimension was not found significant in determining the academic achievement. Jindal(1984)studied the level of education was positively related to students' modernity. Education was good promoter of universalistic and civic dimensions. Sex, father's income and parents' English medium schooling were found to be significantly related to Students' modernity. Ahmad(1979) studied the relationship between value and modernity with special reference to college girls. The findings of this study were that fashion mindedness, achievement orientation and non-conformity were significantly correlated. Tyagi Nishi (2021) studied the attitude of professional Students towards modernization in context of selected variables and found that it is significant to point out that gender and locality are not among the major contribution for the reference in the attitude towards modernization. Sharma (1979) studied that there was the lowest percentage of moderns in the humanities followed by social sciences and professionals. The male students were more modern than female, and the high status students were more modern than the low status students.

Statement of the problem

A Study of Attitude of College Students towards Modernization in relation to Courses of Study.

Objectives-

- To compare the attitude of male and female college students belonging to professional courses towards modernization
- To compare the attitude of male and female college students belonging to non professional courses towards modernization.
- To compare the attitude of college students belonging to professional and non professional courses towards modernization

Hypotheses-

- There is no significant difference between the attitude of male and female college students belonging to professional courses towards modernization.
- There is no significant difference between the attitude of male and female college students belonging to non professional courses towards modernization.
- There is no significant difference between the attitude of college students belonging to professional and non professional courses towards modernization.

Research Method

Descriptive survey method was used in the present study.

Sample

The sample for the present study consisted of 60 college students studying in various professional and non-professional courses in Saharanpur district. 30 students from professional courses and 30 from non-professional courses were taken as sample of the study. They were selected in equal proportion gender-wise. The sample was selected by simple random sampling technique.

Variable: There are two variables. Dependent variable is attitude towards modernization and independent variable is Courses of study (professional and non-professional courses).

Tool Used: Modernization scale constructed by Raghavendra. S. Singh and Amar Nath Tripathi and Ram.J.Lal .

Statistical techniques: Mean, Standard deviation and t-test.

Analysis and interpretation of data-

Table-1

Showing significance of difference between mean scores for attitude of male and female college students belonging to professional courses towards modernization

Group	N	Mean	SD	Df	t value	Level of significance
Male	15	132.33	3.79	28	1.66	Not significant
Female	15	143	5.20			

Table-1 shows that calculated t-value for attitude of male and female college students belonging to professional courses towards modernization is 1.66, which is less than table value at 0.05 level of significance. Hence, there is no significant difference between mean scores of attitude of male and female students belonging to professional courses towards modernization. So hypothesis-1 is accepted. It may be also interpreted that attitude of male and female college students belonging to professional courses towards modernization is similar.

Table-2

Showing significance of difference between mean scores for attitude of male and female college students belonging to non-professional courses towards modernization

Group	N	Mean	SD	Df	t value	Level of significance
Male	15	132.07	17.37	28	0.75	Not significant
Female	15	135.93	9.57			

Table-2 indicates that the calculated t-value for attitude of male and female college students belonging to non-professional courses towards modernization is 0.75, which is less than table value at 0.05 level of significance. So, hypothesis-2 is accepted. Therefore, there is no significant difference between mean scores of attitude of male and female students belonging to non-professional courses towards modernization. It may also be interpreted that attitude of male and female college students of non-professional courses towards modernization is similar.

Table-3

Showing significance of difference between mean scores for attitude of college students belonging to professional and non-professional courses towards modernization.

Group	N	Mean	SD	Df	t value	Level of significance
Male	30	137.67	18.15	58	0.87	Not significant
Female	30	134.00	13.91			

It is clear from Table-3 that the calculated t-value for attitude of college students belonging to professional and non-professional courses towards modernization comes out to be 0.87, which is less than table value at 0.05 level of significance. So, hypothesis-3 is accepted. It indicates that there is no significant difference between the attitude of college students belonging to professional and non-professional courses towards modernization. It may also be interpreted that attitude of college students belonging to professional and non-professional courses towards modernization is similar.

Conclusions

By present study, it is found that the attitude of college students towards modernization is average. It is also concluded that no significant difference was found between the attitude of college students belonging to professional and non-professional courses towards modernization. Male and female students of each course do not differ significantly in their attitude towards modernization. The findings are also supported by study conducted by Nishi Tyagi (2021).

Educational Implications

Modernization has various effects, but it has deep impression in the field of education. It has brought so many new changes in the field of Indian higher education system. The findings of the present study can prove to be very important to assess and improve attitude of college students towards modernization, which certainly results in developing the modern and scientific attitude among students. The modern attitude of students also help them to attain good academic achievement (Kumar, Sushil 2018).

References-

- Ekka.N. (2013) Impact of Modernization on tribal religious, custom and traditions. A case study of Rourkela, M.A thesis
- Gaine, M.V Hafiz (2013) work up on the modernization of higher secondary school with respect to science and social science background
- Sushil Kumar (2018) conducted a thesis of a study of attitude towards modernity and academic achievement of students
- Sexena Danny (2018) conducted a thesis of a study learning style among the students of technical and professional.
- Statistical techniques of analysis (ES-333), IGNOU OPEN UNIVERSITY B.Ed page no 69,70)
- NCERT Journals indian educational research volume 57 (page 54 to 57)
- <http://www.sciencepub.net/> research
- <http://doi.org/10.24297/ijrem.v1i2416>
- <http://doing.org/10.21922/srjhse1.v412>
- www.psychologyandeducation.net
- <https://www.britannica.com/topic/modernization>
- http://ijrar.com/upload_issue/ijrar_issue_1520.pdf
- <https://www.yourarticlelibrary.com/articles/modernisation-introduction-meaning-concept-and-other-details/47757>

